

THE SIMPLE PRESENT TENSE

(Oddiy hozirgi zamon)

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1-son kasb-hunar maktabi ingliz tili fani oʻqituvchisi

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Annotatsiya. Bu maqolada hozirgi zamon shakli THE SIMPLE PRESENT TENSE haqida va bu zamonning ishlatilishi haqida ma'lumotlar tadqiq qilinadi.

Kalit soʻzlar: hozirgi zamon, shaxs, birliklar, fe'l, The Simple Present, I, he, she, do, does, don't, doesn't.

THE SIMPLE PRESENT TENSE

(Simple present tense)

Abstract. This article explores information about THE SIMPLE PRESENT TENSE and its usage.

Key words: present tense, person, units, verb, The Simple Present, I, he, she, do, does, don't, doesn't.

ПРОСТОЕ НАСТОЯЩЕЕ ВРЕМЯ

(Простое настоящее время)

Аннотация. В данной статье рассматривается информация о ПРОСТОМ НАСТОЯЩЕМ ВРЕМЕНИ и его использовании.

Ключевые слова: настоящее время, человек, единицы, глагол, простое настоящее время, я, он, она, делаю, делает, не делает, не делает.

Simple Presentning 3-shaxs birlikdan tashqari barcha shakllari fe'lning asosiy shaklini, (infinitivning to yuklamasi tushirib qoldirilgan shaklini) qo'yish bilan yasaladi. 3-shaxs birlikda fe'lning asosiy shakliga -s qo'shimchasi qo'shiladi: to work I (we, you, they) work, he works.

3-shaxs birlik qo'shimchasi -s jarangli undosh tovushlar va unlilardan keyin [z], jarangsiz undosh tovushlardan keyin [s] deb o'qiladi: He reads [ri:dz]. He sees [si:z]. He writes [raits].

3-shaxs birlikda ss, ch, sh, x harflar (sirg'aluvchi tovushlar) bilan tugagan fe'llarga -es qo'shimchasi qo'shiladi va [iz] deb o'qiladi:

I pass, he passes;

I dress, he dresses;

I teach, he teaches;

I wish, he wishes.

Izoh: Oldida undosh harfi bo'lgan -y harfi bilan tugagan fe'llarga 3-shaxs birlikda -es qo'shimchasi qo'shiladi va y harfi i harfiga aylanadi:

I cry, he cries [kraiz];

I carry, he carries [kariz].

Oldida unli harfi bo'lgan y harfi bilan tugagan fe'llarga 3-shaxs birlikda umumiy qoida asosida -s qo'shimchasi qo'shiladi:

I play, he plays [pleiz].

3-shaxs birlikda to do, to go fe'llariga -es qo'shimchasi qo'shiladi: He goes, he does.

2. Bo'lishsiz shakli asosiy fe'lning oldiga do (does) yordamchi fe'lini va not inkor yuklamasini qo'yish bilan yasaladi:

Ega + do (does) + not + V

I do not work. He does not work.

3. So'roq shakli do yordamchi fe'lini (3-shaxs birlikda does) egadan oldinga qo'yish bilan yasaladi: Do I work? Does he (she) work?

Do Does + ega + V?

4. Og'zaki nutqda quyidagi qisqartirmalar qo'llaniladi:

I don't work.

He (she, it) doesn't.

We (you, they) don't.

ODDIY HOZIRGI (SIMPLE PRESENT) ZAMONNING ISHLATILISHI:

A. Simple Present odatiy, doimiy, egaga xos bo'lgan yoki umuman yuz beradigan ish-harakatini ifodalash uchun ishlatiladi (hozir emas):

1. The postman **brings** us the newspaper in the morning.
2. John **walks** to school every day.
3. The earth **goes** round the sun.
4. An atheist **doesn't** believe in God.
5. What **does** this word mean? He lives in Tashkent.
6. He **speaks** French well.

B. Ingliz tilida davom zamonlarda ishlatilmaydigan **to see, to recognize, to want, to understand** kabi fe'llar bor. Bunday fe'llar bilan hozir, gapirilayotgan paytda davom etayotgan ish harakatni ifodalash uchun Present Continuous emas, Simple Present ishlatiladi:

I **see** a ship in the distance.

Don't **talk** so loudly, I hear you well.

I don't **understand** this sentence.

C. If agar, **unless** agar...-masa, **provided that** bo'lsa, shartda, **when** -da, paytida, **before** oldin, **until** -maguncha, **till** -gacha **as soon as** -gach, **as long as** -da kabi bog'lovchilar bilan bog'langan shart va payt ergash gaplarda Simple Present Simple Future o'rnida kelasi zamondagi ish-harakatni ifodalash uchun ishlatiladi:

If he comes, I shall ask him about it.

I shall go there **unless it rains**.

I shall stay here **until he returns**.

We shall send you the documents **as soon as** we **receive** them from London.

D. Harakatni (qatnovni) ifodalaydigan **to leave** jo'namoq, tark etmoq, **to start** boshlamoq, **to sail** suzib ketmoq, **to return** qaytib kelmoq, **to arrive** yetib kelmoq, **to go** bormoq, **to come** kelmoq kabi fe'llar bilan Simple Present kelasi zamondagi ish-harakatni ifodalaydi. Bunda kelasi zamoni ko'rsatuvchi payt holi bo'lishi kerak:

Does your brother arrive on Monday?

The steamer **sails** tomorrow.

Xulosa qilib aytganda, Simple Present—hozirgi zamon hisoblanib odatiy ish harakatlar, har doim takrorlanib turadigan ish-harakatlarni ifodalashda ishlatiladi. Bu maqolada bu zamon shaklining ishlatil yo'llari ham ko'rsatilib o'tildi.

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